

Our focus

- INNOVATION SUPPORT SERVICES
- SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN (SFSC)
- AGRICULTURAL ADVISORS
- SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS
- AKIS

COREnet & EU4Advice paving the way for the EU SFSC Advisory Network

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Role within AKIS and focus on SFSCs

COREnet and EU4Advice were the first advisory networks (ANs) funded by the Horizon Europe programme in 2022 for well-connected and effective advisory systems in SFSC within the wider AKIS (Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System).

An advisor in SFSC supports farmers in positioning and selling their products in the local marketplace, as well as identifying opportunities for scaling SFSCs performance and impact for better interaction with consumers.

Objectives

The overall objective of the network is to foster exchanges between advisors across EU Member States, more specifically:

- Facilitating **KNOWLEDGE SHARING**
- CAPACITY BUILDING**
- INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS**
- Identification of **INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS** and their **PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION**

Challenges

The challenge is ensuring **effective knowledge transfer** and **information flow** to enhance **innovative practices** and **translate needs into new activities**, while supporting the AN's future usability and financial sustainability after the project concludes.

Future perspectives

COREnet and EU4Advice will continue their mapping and initiatives to have new advisors registered and enlarge the network giving more visibility to SFSC and promoting peer-to-peer learning across Europe.

Building the Network

To build the network, COREnet and EU4Advice have established a proper **multi-actor approach (MAA)**, starting from involved partners and linked entities across EU countries with solid field, research, communication and advisory expertise to attract SFSC advisors to the newly established AN.

The adopted MAA also includes:

- EVENTS**
(European Roadshows, Field Visits, consultation workshops, webinars)
- LIVING LABS**
(in Spain, Ireland, Hungary and The Netherlands)
- FUNDINGS**
for "lighthouse projects"
- TRAINING MATERIALS**
with microcredentials

All resulting powerful in exchanging SFSC good practices (Golden Cases) and innovative tools, as well as in understanding advisors' needs and gaps in AKIS.

650
advisors*

ARE CURRENTLY INVOLVED IN THE SFSC AN, AND THE NUMBER IS EXPECTED TO GROW.

*EU SFSC advisors registered

Advisory Database Map

